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Animal-assisted therapy in patients affected by schizophrenia and schizophrenic-related disorders: A scoping review

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Abstract

Introduction: Schizophrenia poses significant challenges in psychiatric care. Amidst established practices such as pharmacological therapy and psychotherapy, Animal-assisted therapy (AAT) is gaining attention as a potential approach to enhance the psychophysical well-being of patients with schizophrenia. This scoping review aims to map the existing literature on the impact of AAT on schizophrenia, focusing on changes in symptoms and overall well-being of affected individuals and identifying potential areas for intervention and future research.

Methods: A systematic search was conducted from August to September 2023 using a scoping review methodology. The review encompassed international biomedical databases, including PubMed, Cinahl, PsycINFO, and Embase, and incorporated additional resources such as relevant textbooks and gray literature.

Results: The review highlights AAT as a promising co-therapeutic approach, demonstrating benefits across physical, mental, emotional, and social dimensions in schizophrenia patients. It is particularly noted for its potential in alleviating the disorder's negative symptoms.

Discussion and Conclusions: The findings of this scoping review suggest that AAT could play a significant role in treating and managing schizophrenia, enhancing patient well-being and treatment adherence. However, the review also reveals gaps in current research and emphasizes the need for further studies to establish a more robust evidence base. This would aid in better understanding the efficacy of AAT and in integrating it effectively into mental health care practices for schizophrenia.

Take-home message: Animal-assisted therapy seems to improve the psychological well-being of schizophrenic patients.

Keywords: animal-assisted therapy; review; schizophrenia; well-being.

INTRODUCTION

Animal Assisted Therapy (AAT) represents a novel, non-pharmacological approach to therapeutic interventions. Characterized by structured interactions between animals and patients, AAT aims to achieve specific therapeutic goals,

contributing to rehabilitation and psychological well-being [1]. Maujean [2] emphasizes that animals play a pivotal role in these therapeutic processes, adapting to the varied settings, durations, and activities tailored to individual needs. Sessions can be conducted in diverse environments such as clinics, hospitals, nursing homes, and private settings, incorporating activities ranging from games to more direct animal care [3].

The Italian “Istituto Superiore di Sanità” recognizes AAT for its multifaceted impact on physical, neurological, cognitive, emotional, and relational disorders across a spectrum of pathologies [4]. This comprehensive approach necessitates a multi-disciplinary team, including veterinary specialists, therapists, and healthcare professionals, to fully harness the therapeutic potential of the animal-patient relationship.

Distinct from general pet ownership, AAT involves more structured and goal-oriented activities, including animal-assisted activities (playing sports with animals under supervision) and more comprehensive animal-assisted interventions that blend AAT with health education programs. The latter has been noted to be highly effective, particularly in rehabilitation [5,6].

The applicability of AAT extends to a range of animals beyond the commonly used dogs, including horses (hippotherapy), cats, fish, dolphins, rabbits, and birds. This diversity allows AAT to cater to varied individual preferences and therapeutic needs [7]. However, despite its increasing popularity, the Efficacy of AAT, particularly in complex mental health conditions like schizophrenia, remains an area of ongoing research [8].

Schizophrenia, as defined by the World Health Organization (WHO), affects approximately 24 million people globally and manifests in a broad spectrum of symptoms, including delusions, hallucinations, thought and language disorders, and cognitive deficits. Schizophrenia and similar psychotic conditions manifest through three key symptom types: positive, negative, and cognitive impairments. Positive symptoms include hallucinations, delusions, and incoherent speech, whereas negative symptoms encompass lack of motivation, inability to experience pleasure, and emotional dullness. Factors such as genetic vulnerability, drug abuse, traumatic experiences, and intense stress contribute to the likelihood of developing a severe psychotic disorder [4]. The etiology of schizophrenia is complex, involving a mix of genetic and environmental factors, and often leads to significant challenges in treatment adherence and psychosocial functioning [9].

Conventional treatments for schizophrenia typically combine antipsychotic medications with psychotherapy, often cognitive-behavioral therapy [10]. However, the persistence of negative and cognitive symptoms has led to exploring additional co-therapeutic strategies like AAT to enhance overall treatment efficacy [1,11].

This scoping review, therefore, aims to assess the current evidence regarding the impact of AAT on the psychophysical well-being of individuals suffering from schizophrenia.

METHODS

Study design and procedure

This scoping review followed established guidelines for scoping reviews [12]. The aim was to explore the breadth and depth of literature on AAT in the treatment of schizophrenia. Scoping reviews are particularly suited for emerging research areas to map the existing literature and identify key concepts, sources, and gaps.

Search strategy

A comprehensive literature search was performed across several databases, including PubMed, Cinahl, PsycINFO, and Embase. The search strategy utilized a combination of keywords: "Animal Assisted Therapy," "schizophrenia," "pet therapy," "treatment effects," "animal-assisted service," "animal-assisted activity," and "dog." The search was conducted over two months, from August to September 2023.

Selection criteria

The inclusion and exclusion criteria were established to focus on relevant studies:

Inclusion criteria:

Articles published in English.

Studies involving children or adult subjects diagnosed with schizophrenia or schizophrenia-related disorders.

Research including AAT as an intervention.

Articles presenting primary data or reviews.

Exclusion criteria:

Studies not involving human participants.

Articles not available in full text.

Non-English language publications.

Studies regarding different psychological disturbances including schizophrenia or schizophrenia-related disorders.

Data charting and collection

Data were charted from each included study using a form designed for this review. Key information extracted included author(s), year of publication, country, study design, sample size, details of AAT interventions, measured outcomes, and main findings.

Analysis and presentation of data

The results were analyzed to map out the key themes, trends, and gaps in the literature. The findings were categorized and synthesized narratively, focusing on the characteristics of the studies, types of AAT interventions, outcomes, and overall conclusions drawn from the literature.

RESULTS

Our scoping review of AATs in the treatment of schizophrenia encompassed a diverse array of studies (n = 12), including 2 systematic reviews, 4 randomized controlled trials (RCTs), 1 cross-sectional study, 2 qualitative analyses, 2 pilot studies and 1 clinical trial. These studies collectively provided a comprehensive overview of the impact of various forms of AAT, such as equine-assisted interventions, dog-assisted therapies, and hippotherapy, on individuals diagnosed with schizophrenia and related disorders.

To provide a clearer understanding of the specific impacts of AAT on schizophrenia, Table 1 summarizes key studies in this area, highlighting their design, sample size, type of AATs, and the main results.

Table 1. Summary of key studies on the efficacy of animal-assisted therapy in schizophrenia treatment.

Authors and year	Study Design	Type of AATs	Results
Barak et al. (2001) [13]	RCT	AAT was conducted in weekly 4-hour sessions. Subjects were 10 elderly schizophrenic patients and 10 matched patients (mean age: 79.1±6.7 years).	Treatment encouraged mobility, interpersonal contact, and communication and reinforced activities of daily living (ADLs), including personal hygiene and independent self-care, through the use of cats and dogs as “modeling companions.” The Social Adaptive Functioning Evaluation (SAFE) scores increase in the group subjected to animal therapy: from p = 0.003 to p = 0.001.
Calvo et al. (2016) [14]	RCT	Twenty-two institutionalized patients with chronic schizophrenia completed the 6-month rehabilitation program, which included individual psychotherapy, group therapy, a functional program (intended to improve daily functioning), a community program (intended to facilitate community reintegration) and a family program.	At the end of the program, both groups (control and AAT-treatment) showed significant improvements in positive and overall symptomatology, as measured with the Positive and Negative Syndrome Scale PANSS, but only the AAT-treatment group showed a significant improvement in negative symptomatology. Cortisol level was significantly reduced after participating in an AAT session, which could indicate that interaction with the therapy dogs reduced stress.
Cerino et al. (2011) [15]	Clinical Trial	Twenty-four subjects with a diagnosis of schizophrenia were enrolled for a 1 year-treatment involving therapeutic riding sessions. All subjects were tested at the beginning and at the end of treatment with a series of validated test	The results reveal a persistent state of regression of the pathology with regards to negative symptoms, together with a decrease in hospitalization days. The pre-treatment BPRS value was 80.1, reduced to 57.1 for one patient (t = -4.663; p < 0.005) and 69.1 for the rest of the group (t = -4.572; p < 0.001) at the end of treatment. The PANSS reports a change from 33.3% to 25.9% at the end of treatment (t= - 5.032; p = <0.001).

		batteries (BPRS and 8 items-PANSS).	
Chen et al. (2022) [16]	RCT	Forty participants were randomly assigned to either the AAT or control group. The AAT group participated in one-hour sessions with dog-assisted group activities once a week for 12 weeks. The controls participated in dose-matched, non-animal-related recreational activities. Both groups remained on their usual psychotropic medication during the trial.	The AAT group showed a greater increase in lower extremity strength and social skills, but no improvement in cognitive function, agility, or mobility.
Corring et al. (2010) [7]	Qualitative study	A sample of 6 ACT patients with schizophrenia or schizoaffective disorder who reside in the community and 6 mental health care staff participated in 10 weeks of weekly horseback riding sessions with an experienced THBR instructor	THR was effective in patients with schizophrenia as they gained enjoyment, developed a relationship with the horse, learned new skills and increased their level of self-esteem.
Corring et al. (2013) [17]	Qualitative study	A sample of 6 ACT patients with schizophrenia or schizoaffective disorder who reside in the community and 6 mental health care staff participated in 10 weeks of weekly horseback riding sessions with an experienced THBR instructor.	The study shows that horseback riding is useful for patients suffering from schizophrenia, as they have fun, increase self-confidence and create a bond with the animal.
Jormfeldt et al (2018) [18]	Systematic review of 6 studies	Equine-assisted interventions among individuals diagnosed with schizophrenia	The findings of the six included articles indicate that therapeutic equine assisted interventions could be beneficial for individuals with severe mental illness such as schizophrenia or schizophrenia like disorders.
Kovacs et al. (2004) [19]	Pilot study	Weekly sessions of animal-assisted therapy for a nine-month period, each therapeutic session lasting for 50 minutes on 7 schizophrenic patients	After completion of therapy there were significant improvements in home and daily living activities.

		living in a social institution	
Lang et al. (2010) [20]	Cross-sectional study	Dog-assisted interviews in 14 acute schizophrenic patients	Anxiety, measured with the STAI in 14 was reduced after the interview with the presence of a dog when compared to the control interview situation (F=106.19; df =1; p< 0.0001),
Nathans-Barel et al. (2005) [21]	Pilot study	The hedonic tone of 10 chronic schizophrenia patients who participated in 10 weekly interactive sessions of AAT was compared to a control group treated without animal assistance.	The group subjected to AAT demonstrated a significant improvement in anhedonic tone compared to the control group (ANCOVA df = 1, 17, F= 6.30 p = 0.02).
Seredova et al. (2016) [22]	RCT	25 patients with paranoid schizophrenia, or acute and transient psychotic disorders attended 90 minutes hippotherapy sessions two days a week for a period of three weeks	Hippotherapy increased well-being (F = 7.81, P = 0.007) and the differences between the well-being scores before and after the treatments increased with treatment repetitions (F = 7.81, P = 0.007). The effect hippotherapy was statistically significant for all well-being characteristics except for tension in the first treatment and contact in the second treatment
Tyssedal et al. (2023) [11]	Systematic review of 12 RCTs and non-RCTS	Dog-assisted interventions for adults diagnosed with schizophrenia and related disorders.	General psychopathology, positive and negative symptoms of psychosis, anxiety, stress, self-esteem, self-determination, lower physical strength, social functioning, and quality of life were among the most significant outcome measures in terms of improvement.

The included studies collectively underscore the potential of AAT as a co-therapeutic approach for schizophrenia, contributing to improved psychosocial functioning and quality of life.

Tyssedal et al.'s review [11] of 12 RCTs and non-RCTs showed improvements in various aspects such as general psychopathology, positive and negative symptoms, anxiety, stress, self-esteem, and social functioning in adults diagnosed with schizophrenia. In this review, quality of evidence was graded low or very low for all outcome measures. Indeed, low number of participants, heterogeneity, and risk of bias complicate the interpretation of results.

Jormfeldt et al.'s [18] systematic review indicated that equine-assisted therapies could be beneficial for individuals with severe mental illnesses like schizophrenia, enhancing their overall well-being.

Studies like Corring et al.'s qualitative analyses [7,17] demonstrated that THR was effective in increasing self-esteem and developing new skills among patients with schizophrenia. Several studies, including those by Calvo et al. [14] and Chen et al [16], reported significant improvements in negative symptoms of schizophrenia and overall well-being following AAT sessions. AAT was found to increase social skills and physical strength among participants but showed varying results regarding cognitive functions and agility. Kovacs et al.'s pilot study [19] reported improvements in daily living activities among schizophrenic patients after AAT therapy. Nathans-Barel et al.'s [21] study demonstrated significant improvements in anhedonic tone, an important aspect of schizophrenia, through AAT. Cerino et al.'s [15] clinical trial indicated a regression in negative symptoms and a decrease in hospitalization days after a year-long treatment involving therapeutic riding sessions.

Seredova et al.'s RCT [22] showed that hippotherapy increased well-being in patients with paranoid schizophrenia, with repeated treatments enhancing the effect. Barak et al.'s RCT highlighted that AAT facilitated mobility, interpersonal contact, and reinforced activities of daily living, improving Social Adaptive Functioning Evaluation scores.

DISCUSSION

This scoping review mapped the current landscape of AAT in the treatment of schizophrenia, revealing diverse approaches and outcomes. The literature predominantly indicates a positive impact of AAT on schizophrenia, aligning with previous studies highlighting the benefits of AAT in various psychiatric conditions [23,24].

In literature, frequent interactions with animals, coupled with activities focused on self-care, have been shown to boost patients' self-esteem, leading to increased activity and responsibility in their personal affairs [25,26]. Another study highlighted progress in emotional symptoms and various facets of self-perception and self-image [27]. A critical aspect of this approach is its ability to yield tangible benefits in areas where conventional treatments may fall short. This is particularly evident in treating the symptom of anhedonia in patients, which significantly impacts their daily life quality [25].

In the 2022 study by Monfort et al. [28], a randomized controlled trial (RCT) was conducted where Animal-Assisted Therapy (AAT) was administered over a period of three months in patients affected by depression and schizophrenia. This therapy included a series of 10 sessions, held weekly, with each group comprising up to 10 patients. The study reported notable results, including a significant reduction in the positive symptoms of psychosis ($F: 27.80, p = 0.001$), as well as a marked improvement in patient functionality ($F: 26.70, p < 0.001$) as the therapy sessions progressed.

Engagement of patients with schizophrenia in animal therapy has shown beneficial effects on anhedonia, a symptom of the disorder characterized by a diminished ability to find pleasure in normally enjoyable activities and situations. In psychiatric institutions, the introduction of animal therapy programs for individuals with schizophrenia has become increasingly favored over other treatment approaches. Participation in these programs has been linked to a reduction in apathy and the lessening of negative symptoms associated with the condition.

Our scoping review of AAT in schizophrenia treatment revealed several key findings across a range of studies. AAT interventions, particularly dog-assisted therapies, showed significant improvements in the negative symptoms of schizophrenia, such as social withdrawal and apathy. Participants who underwent AAT exhibited reductions in general psychopathological symptoms. This included a decrease in both positive and negative symptoms of psychosis. Studies reported that AAT led to better social functioning and overall quality of life in schizophrenia patients, improving interpersonal communication and enhancing mobility. Notable reductions in stress and anxiety levels were observed following AAT sessions, with some studies, such as that by Calvo et al. [14], noting lowered cortisol levels, indicating reduced stress. AAT also had physical health benefits, such as increased lower extremity strength, particularly noted in patients engaging in dog-assisted group activities. Some studies highlighted improvements in daily living activities and self-care skills post-AAT, although enhancements in cognitive functions were not consistently reported. Emotional symptoms and hedonic tone improvements were evident in participants, indicating enhanced emotional well-being following AAT. AAT was generally well-received by patients, indicating a higher level of treatment adherence and acceptability compared to some traditional therapies.

The findings from this review suggest that AAT can be a valuable adjunct to conventional treatments for schizophrenia. The observed benefits in social functioning and symptom management highlight AAT's potential to complement pharmacotherapy and psychotherapy. This integration could particularly benefit patients who exhibit negative symptoms or have limited responsiveness to traditional treatments. However, it is crucial for clinicians to consider individual patient preferences and specific needs when integrating AAT into treatment plans. The choice of animal, the nature of activities, and the frequency of sessions should be tailored to each patient's unique condition and circumstances.

The International Association of Human-Animal Interaction Organizations (IAHAIO) has issued comprehensive guidelines for conducting animal-assisted interventions (AAI) [29]. These directives specify that AAIs should be purposeful and structured, aiming for therapeutic outcomes. Within the scope of AAI, AAT and animal-assisted activity (AAA) are two distinct forms relevant to healthcare. AAT is characterized by its planned, quantifiable, and recorded nature, while AAA involves more casual and informal interactions. The guidelines also clarify that AAT focuses on improving physical, cognitive, behavioral, and socio-emotional aspects, whereas AAA primarily enhances motivation, education, and recreational experiences.

The quality of studies on this topic varied, with some providing robust evidence through controlled methodologies, while others were qualitative or pilot studies with smaller sample sizes. This variation in study design and quality highlights the need for more rigorous research in this field. Standardized protocols and outcome measures would enhance the comparability and generalizability of future studies.

Despite the positive indications, there are significant gaps in the literature. There is a need for larger, long-term studies to ascertain the sustained effects of AAT and its impact on different stages and subtypes of schizophrenia. Future research should also explore the mechanisms underlying the observed benefits, such as neurobiological changes and psychosocial factors.

Additionally, the variability in AAT implementation across different settings calls for research on best practices and standardization in this therapy modality. Studies that compare different types of animals and intervention models would provide valuable insights into optimizing AAT for schizophrenia patients.

The inclusion of animals in therapy introduces unique ethical considerations. It is essential to ensure the welfare of the animals involved and to establish guidelines for their care and handling. Ethical considerations also extend to the patients, particularly in obtaining informed consent and ensuring that the therapy aligns with their preferences and beliefs.

This review has several limitations. Firstly, the exclusion of non-English language and gray literature studies, as well as mixed studies (AAT on patients affected by depression, schizophrenic, and other psychological disorders in the same intervention) may have omitted relevant findings. Secondly, the heterogeneity in study designs and outcomes makes it challenging to draw definitive conclusions. Finally, the scoping nature of this review limits the depth of analysis on specific aspects of AAT in schizophrenia.

CONCLUSION

The review found a variety of AAT interventions using different animals and settings, suggesting customizable approaches based on individual patient needs and preferences. Despite the positive outcomes, there were gaps in the research, particularly the need for more long-term studies and randomized controlled trials to establish a more comprehensive understanding of AAT's efficacy in schizophrenia treatment. Overall, the review underscores the potential of AAT as a beneficial co-therapeutic approach in schizophrenia, offering improvements across psychological, social, emotional, and physical health dimensions [30-36]. However, it also highlights the necessity for further research to integrate AAT effectively into psychiatric care for schizophrenia.

In conclusion, this scoping review underscores the potential of AAT as a beneficial intervention for patients with schizophrenia. While the current evidence is promising, further research is required to solidify these findings and guide clinical implementation. The integration of AAT into schizophrenia treatment regimens could enhance patient outcomes and offer a holistic approach to mental health care.

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